

Original Article

Effect of Economic Globalization on Human Development: Evidence from South East Asian States

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Abstract

This research is intended to examine the effect of globalization on human development in emerging nations. The objective has been attained by examining 20 years data (from 2000-2019) of six Southeast Asian states (Cambodia, Indonesia, Malaysia, Myanmar, Philippines, and Thailand) associated in ASEAN trade block. Brunei and Singapore were not included in the study because both are developed nations. Vietnam, however, is not a fully developed country but it is regarded as a high-income earning country. Laos was also eliminated from the estimation because of the absence of data. The core variables are trade liberalization and FDI, which are used as a substitute for globalization. Other predictor variables are death rate, government expenditure on health and dependency ratio. The result of Hausman test showed that the fixed effect model is suitable for this study. The results of fixed effect evaluation confirmed that both FDI and trade openness has an adverse impact on Human Development in selected Southeast Asian states.

Keywords: *Globalization, Human Development, Trade Liberalization, Foreign Direct Investment*

Introduction

The repercussions of globalization vary from nation to nation, clearly differentiating between industrialized and developing nations. Globalization helps economies grow by creating jobs, opening new markets, maximizing the use of resources, and disseminating technological knowledge, but it does not ensure the advancement of humanity because its effects are heavily dependent on the social and administrative conditions of each country.

Though globalization has cleared the way for development on a worldwide scale, certain states are seeing faster economic growth than others (Lee & Vivarelli, 2006). This suggests that not every nation benefits equally from globalization. The developed world gains more from it, while the poor world suffers more. Globalization is widening the income inequality between the rich and the deprived. Just 20% of the world's population lived in the richest states in the 1960s, and their combined wealth was thirty times more than that of 80% of the world's poorest citizens. However, by 1995, the richest 20% of people had 82 times more wealth than the bottom 80% (Karras, 2003). Economic globalization is the expression used to define the far-off movements of goods, resources, info, and services; political globalization is the phenomenon used to explain the spread of administrative policies; and social globalization is the expression used to elucidate the spread of cultural values, the blending of ideas, and the movement of people. These are the three dimensions of globalization. The primary focus of this study is the economic side of globalization, which includes trade and foreign investments. These factors directly and strongly affect HDI, as they raise living standards by reducing import prices, which in turn raises per capita income and reduces poverty. However, another perspective uses actual evidence to support negative effects including inequality and financial instability. Many schools of

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thought have examined how globalization has affected society, and numerous hypotheses have been put forth in this debate.

Per capita GDP was widely employed to calculate the Human Development of different states in the 1950s. However, by the early 1980s, it was realized that a single macroeconomic indicator was inadequate to quantify the multidimensionality of human development because it could not adequately capture its essence. Consequently, in their report from 1990, UNDP unveiled the HDI (Human Development Index), a new and all-encompassing indicator of human advancement. Recent studies have also emphasized the role of institutional governance structures, such as board diversity and regulatory capacity, in moderating the impacts of globalization on human development (Arif, 2023). In the study, it was discussed that although people's options are infinite and subject to change, three essentials must be met for everyone to lead a decent life: health, education, and a reasonable standard of living. Numerous choices remain unapproachable to people if these rudiments are not met.

ASEAN, an economic union of ten South Asian republics (the Philippines, Indonesia, Cambodia, Malaysia, Thailand, Brunei, Myanmar, Laos, Vietnam, and Singapore), fosters economic, academic, and societal integration amongst its member states in Asia and intergovernmental cooperation. The main goal of ASEAN was to boost economic growth, which in turn speeds up societal development. It also aims to advance stability and peace. When it was established in 1967, ASEAN was one of the world's most interconnected regional commercial blocks, distinguished by a rising number of cooperation relationships between its member nations. Even while the KOF globalization index has been rising for ASEAN members since the region's founding, GDP growth and development have not always followed.

Finding out if economic globalization has a positive, adverse, or neutral effect on human development is the main goal of the study for developing nations. The study identifies the features that support the influence of economic globalization in emerging nations in addition to highlighting the internal characteristics of developing countries that influence the HDI and globalization relationship. Leadership dynamics, such as CEO power and board control, also influence how firms and economies respond to external forces like globalization (Arif et al., 2023).

Following the introduction in Section 1, the theoretical and empirical literature has been reviewed in Section 2 and Section 3, respectively. In section 4 the methodology of research is covered. The conceptual model is displayed in section 5. Section 6, presented the estimation results. Section 7, provides the conclusion along with the policy implications. The limitations and guidelines for extension of research are presented in section 8 and 9 respectively

Review of Theoretical Literature

The ideas of growth and trade originated with mercantilism. Mercantilists believe that government regulation and control over trade and economic activity is the only path to national prosperity. It means building wealth, forging favorable trade agreements with foreign nations, and optimizing domestic resources. The best way to increase our wealth, according to English mercantilist author Thomas Mun, is through international trade, where we must strictly adhere to the following rule: we should sell more goods to foreign countries each year than we pay for goods we buy from them. He advocates that the nation's administration plays a proactive role in the economy by boosting exports and controlling imports, especially through trade restrictions (Mun, 1930). Adam Smith and David Hume opposed mercantilism, arguing that trade benefits all parties. In *The Wealth of Nations* (1776), Smith criticized mercantilism's zero-sum view and condemned government–industry collusion as harmful to the public.

When he first proposed the concept of comparative advantage in 1817, David Ricardo clarified that a country's ability to engage in global trade and most global trade stems from its comparative advantage rather than its absolute advantage. According to his theory, when two economies engage in open commerce and are

skilled in producing two goods, one will upsurge its consumption by exporting the goods for which it has a relative advantage and trading in the other commodity (Aldrich, 2004).

In the late 1970s, a theory of global trade was introduced that highlighted the significance of increasing returns to scale. The new commerce theory was the name given to this theory. The theory states that by enacting protectionist measures to establish a sizable industrial base in particular industries, those industries will be able to control the global market. The New Trade Theory prioritizes company diversity above discrete firms and plants in a global competitive environment, in contrast to Classical and Keynesian trade theories. because while some companies export, others do not. Many businesses finance projects directly in other nations with the goal of producing and selling goods there. Conversely, other companies are only concerned with exports. The New Trade Theory looks for the causes of these differences. New Trade philosophers argue that protectionist strategies could create a massive industrial base in particular businesses, allowing those businesses to dominate the world market through a network effect, in response to the concept of decreasing returns to scale (Markusen & Venables, 1998). It has been anticipated that future theories will overcome these restrictions. Sound corporate governance structures are also critical for translating globalization policies into developmental outcomes (Arif et al., 2023).

Review of Empirical Literature

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There is a wide range of research on how globalization affects developing nations. While some studies analyzed globalization, others evaluated it according to its various facets, including political, social, and

economic. Bumbure (2014) examined data from 1991 to 2012 to determine how globalization affected developing nations, or the Baltic states—Estonia, Latvia, and Lithuania. The data showed that the Baltic States have experienced both positive and negative effects from globalization. Through raising GDP per capita and enhancing living conditions, globalization aided in economic expansion. But progress comes at a price: increased unemployment, income disparity, and depletion of human capital.

Awdel and colleagues (2020) provided a theoretical explanation of how globalization affects economic dominion. He said that trade liberalization only helps rich economies and robs developing nations of their sovereignty because they have limited exports and no control over the terms of trade. As a result, they face a trade deficit that gives rich nations political clout over poor developing nations and lessens their own sovereignty. Globalization is unavoidable, despite all the drawbacks, which makes the anticipated fast-paced, cutthroat, and demanding global workplace frightening. Dahlman (2007) argues that emerging nations should have to invest more in ICT infrastructure, physical infrastructure, and human capital. Moreover, drawing attention to the disparity between rich and poor nations, developing nations are advised to enhance social safety and foster innovation and modernization in order to reap the benefits of globalization. Fintech is one such innovation that has enhanced the competitiveness and performance of the banking sector in Pakistan by modernizing financial services and encouraging digital transformation (Ahmed et al., 2024).

In addition to how globalization affects underdeveloped nations in an effort to address a variety of concerns about how globalization has affected the global economy, Akram et al. (2011) conducted a thorough examination of the many phases of economic development. Financial structures and valuation systems are also critical in determining how global financial integration impacts development outcomes (Ali et al., 2022). It has been discovered that globalization has had a variety of effects on the global economy, both directly and indirectly. It has boosted the trend of MNCs and made the global market more realistic. Even if it is decreasing poverty, the world is becoming more unequal since organizations like the WTO, IMF, and UN are in charge of everything. In the modern day, globalization is unavoidable despite dubious cultural impacts and detrimental environmental effects.

Using annual data from the five rising economies, or BRICS, during 1993-2016, Raghutla (2020) examined the impact of free trade on economic progress. The findings of panel estimate showed how frequently the components had long-term correlations. The occurrence of unidirectional causation from economic success to trade liberalization and from economic advancement to financial growth is approved by the heterogeneous panel non-causality assessment. The relationship between inflation and economic growth however remains two-sided i.e. there is a causal relationship between the two. As such, the analysis made a conclusion that economic progress, trade liberalization, expansion of finance, inflation, technology and labor force all have positive correlations. The previous study by Raghutla et al. (2018) also proved the same theory.

Using data from 179 states in 2015, Tang et al. (2020) provided an explanation of how globalization affects nations' sustainable development. In order to determine if countries with higher levels of globalization advance more slowly over time, the research correlated sustainability index with the KOF Indices of Globalization. Compared to other sustainability indices, like the Red List Indices (RLI) and the Environment Sustainability Indices (ESI), some, like the Human Development Indices (HDI) and the Environmental Performance Indices (EPI), show a stronger correlation with different phases of globalization. The results demonstrate that globalization has generally favorable effects on sustainability. Zeren and Ari's (2013) research, which focused on G7 nations, confirmed a twofold causal relationship between globalization and the progress of the economy.

The terms "quality of life," "living standard," "socioeconomic well-being," and "human development" are interchangeable. Though they are not the same, the ideas are connected. Literature demonstrated the profound effects of globalization on various facets of human growth. Using Morlet's partial and multiple wavelet coherence techniques, Haseeb et al. (2020) studied the connection between globalization, human

development, and income disparity in Indonesia. The research made use of monthly data for the years 1990–2016. Wavelet coherences and substantial robust leads lag connections were displayed at the frequency-domain site. The outcome displays a strong but erratic relationship in the temporal domain. Income disparity rises as a result of globalization, according to time-series data. Similarly, Sabi (2007) emphasized that the influence of globalization on human progress is only noticeable until a nation reaches a particular income status, citing economic deregulation as a factor of the social outcome of globalization.

Comparative studies of Singapore, Japan, and India were started by Dash et al. (2018) in order to determine how financial globalization affects advancement of humanity. The analysis determined that in India and Japan, 1991 represented the transition from the pre-globalization to the post-globalization era. In contrast, the years 1962 to 1989 were considered to be Singapore's pre-globalization era, while the years 1989 to 2014 were considered to be its post-globalization age. Regression estimation and the students' T-test were used to verify the hypothesis. Results verify that financial globalization has a major impact on the measures of human advancement. However, depending on the stylized aspect of the economy, its severity varies from nation to nation. In contradiction to this, Dowrick and Golley (2004) developed a three-equation model and examined how trade affected various nations at various times. According to the study, domestic policies and institutional differences between industrialized and developing nations account for the disparity in how globalization has affected them.

Focusing on the interconnection between human capital and development, Olagunju et al. (2019) examined the data of 110 developing countries and concluded that not only do investments in education and health increase economic capacity but also contribute to the general benefits of globalization intensification. Likewise, following the same line of use of annual data of Pakistan and India between the period 1970 and 1994, Abbas and Mukhtar (2000) evaluated the effect of human capital on economic growth based on two empirical models. The former introduced human capital as a direct factor of growth accounting, and the latter allowed human capital to be a complement of physical capital investments. It enabled them to show that higher school enrolment, which is a proxy of human capital X , has a positive effect on economic development, and that human and physical capital have a significant dependence in long-run growth paths.

Research Methodology

This study follows a positivist approach. It assumes that social and economic realities can be measured objectively. Quantitative data and statistical methods are used to test the relationship between globalization and human development (Ali et al., 2022). In order to investigate the effect of economic globalization on human advancement over the period of 2000 - 2019, data from six developing Southeast Asian states were sourced from the official websites of the UNDP and WDI data bank. The study represented globalization and the HDI as a measure of human advancement using a variety of economic and demographic indicators, such as trade openness and foreign investment. The aforementioned sources also provided information on other variables, such as the death rate, government health spending, and dependence ratio. Only six ASEAN nations—Cambodia, Malaysia, Indonesia, Philippines, Myanmar, and Thailand—were taken into account for our analysis; Vietnam and Laos were left out due to a lack of data. Additionally, we eliminated Singapore and Brunei from our list of nations to analyze since they are developed and do not address the goal of our study, which is to ascertain how globalization affects the human development of emerging economies.

In order to examine whether the Random or the Common effect is superior in this study, we used the Breusch-Pagan test after estimating the model using PLS. When the p-value is greater than 0.05, the Common Effect model is used. In this calculation, the intercept is not affected by the cross-sectional or time effect results. As a result, we estimate the equation using the PLS approach and do not do any additional tests for model selection. Lastly, we use the Jarque-Berra test for normalcy to see if the model fits well.

The Conceptual Model

This study aims to determine how economic globalization affects human development. As a result, the variables related to additional aspects of globalization, such as societal and political aspects are included in the model.

$$HDI = f(X_i, \dots, X_j, \dots) \quad (1)$$

Where, X_i denotes the core variables

X_j denotes other predictor variables

Discussion of Result

The outcome demonstrates that foreign direct investment (FDI) significantly lowers the HDI. The coefficient of -0.0075 directs that there will be a 0.75% decline in the human development indices for every 1% upsurge in foreign direct investment. Additionally, there is a strong inverse association between trade openness and the HDI. Any 1% rise in trade liberalization will result in a 0.05% decrease in the HDI, as the coefficient of openness (0.0005) shows. The result also shows that log changes in death rates have a detrimental effect, with each 1% increase in death rates leading to a 37% decrease in human growth. The increase in the dependency ratio, which gauges the proportion of the reliant people to the total population, also significantly lowers the HDI. With a 1% rise in dependency ratio, the HDI falls by 24%, according to the log dependence ratio's coefficient of 0.2475. Nevertheless, health spending is the only predictor variable in the equation that has a positive correlation with the HDI. The human development index rises by 4.7% for every unit that the government spends more on health care.

Table 1: Pooled Ordinary Least Square

Table 1

Results of Pooled OLS Regression Analysis

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Constant (C)	2.34	0.06	37.61	0.000
FDI	-0.01	0.00	-12.93	0.000
Trade Openness	-0.00	0.00	-7.31	0.000
Loan-to-Deposit Ratio (LDR)	-0.38	0.01	-35.02	0.000
Log of Deposits (LDEP)	-0.25	0.01	-17.86	0.000
Health Expenditure (HE)	0.05	0.00	10.15	0.000
Statistic	Value			
R-squared (R ²)	0.97			
Adjusted R-squared (Adj. R ²)	0.97			
F-statistic	713.43			
Prob (F-statistic)	0.0000			
Durbin-Watson Statistic	0.82			
Dependent Variable	HDI			

With an adj R2 of 0.9693, the results show that 97% of the discrepancy in the response variable can be described by the predictor variables. With an F-status of 1%, it is clear that the model does a good job of fitting the data.

Table 2: LM Tests for Random Effects

	Cross-section	Period	Both
B-P test	2.4233 (0.119)	1.1012 (0.294)	3.5245 (0.061)

It is desirable to decide which model is better to use: Common Effect model or Random Effect model, using Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test model. The null hypothesis the LM test presupposes is that the specification according to the Common Effect turns out to be the right one. In case the p-value is greater than the 0.05 measure, the null hypothesis is allowed to accept, and this provides a good indication indicating that the Pooled Least Squares (PLS) approach is sufficient in estimating the model. In contrast, when p-value is less than 0.05 then null hypothesis is rejected, and the Random Effect model is accepted which advises that the variation between entities can strongly influence the model and must be considered. Moreover, in case both the cross-sectional effects and effects specific to time do not affect the intercept in a significant manner, it can be stated that it may not be necessary to select the model. In this instance, one can estimate directly based on either the Pooled OLS or PLS method.

Figure 1: Histogram for Normality

Skewness	Kurtosis	Jarque-Bera	Probability
0.2205	3.2114	1.1860	0.5526

The J-B test assesses if the skewness and kurtosis of the data are comparable to those of a standard distribution. The null hypothesis put out by Jarque-Bera states that the series' distribution is normal. The test result is non-negative in every instance. If the value is far from zero, it indicates that the data distribution is not normal. Tests for normality are used to confirm whether the likelihood that a random variable underpinning a data set is normally distributed and to check if a collection of statistics is well-modeled by a normal distribution. To put it briefly, the tests determine which model to use based on how well a normal model fits the data. There are numerous ways to understand them. In the event that the fit is insufficient, the data are not properly characterized by a normal distribution in that sense, independent of any underlying variable. The distribution's normality is confirmed by the Jarque-Bera test result.

Conclusion and Policy Implications

Using panel data estimation techniques, we examine the sample of six emerging Southeast Asian states over a 20-year period from 2000 to 2019. Our findings indicate that the Index of Human Development in ASEAN is significantly impacted negatively by foreign investment, open trade, the death rate, and the dependency ratio. The findings are consistent with research by Bumbure (2014) and Awdel et al. (2020), whereas it defies Lee & Vivarelli's (2006) conclusions. The only relevant element that positively affects the developing nations' ASEAN trading bloc index of human development is government spending on health. The findings align with the research conducted by Olagunju et al. (2019) and Abbas and Mukhtar

(2000). The overall finding indicates that human development in ASEAN countries is negatively impacted by globalization.

Based on the acquired results, the study proposed that the general well-being of all citizens— which includes both economic prosperity and individual quality of life, should be the basis for decisions about trade or economic liberalization. To reap long-term benefits, the report also recommended increasing government spending on development and health. In order to achieve price stability and monetary autonomy, macroeconomic decisions should also be taken with this in mind. This is necessary if economic growth is achieved.

Limitations

Because they are among the first to show how economic globalization affects human advancement in developing ASEAN countries, all of the thesis's conclusions are revolutionary. It is important to remember that these cannot be applied uniformly to all of the trade blocs member states. Due to data limitations, this study's duration is restricted because data from some developing nations were not accessible. Longer sample spans could yield far more trustworthy results. Although there are many social and cultural advantages and disadvantages to globalization, this study primarily looks at its effects on the economy.

Direction for Further Research

Undoubtedly, the research yielded significant results, but it also raised new questions that need to be clarified in other studies. In line with the conclusions drawn from this study. To assess the validity of the research's findings, it is advised to conduct a follow-up study on a comparable sample after a predetermined amount of time. Longer time periods and comparisons can be used to further expand the research and confirm or refute the constancy of the findings. It is advised to use various quantitative analytic techniques on the same sample of countries throughout the same time period. It is possible to perform an analogous study (sample, time, technique) using alternative control variables or modified model parameters

References

- Abbas, Q., & Mujahid-Mukhtar, E. (2000). The Role of Human Capital in Economic Growth: A Comparative Study of Pakistan and India [with Comments]. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 39(4), 451–473. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/41260279>
- Ahmed, M., Kumar, A., Talha, M., Akram, Z., & Arif, K. (2024). Impact of fintech on the Pakistani banking sector. *Journal of Economic Info*, 11(1), 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.31580/ek5dnd23>
- Akram, M. Faheem, M. A. Dost, M. K. & Abdullah, Q. (2011). *Globalization and its Impacts on the World Economic Development*: International Journal of Business and Social Science. 2 (23), 291-297. https://ijbssnet.com/view.php?u=http://ijbssnet.com/journals/Vol_2_No_23_Special_Issue_December_2_011/36.pdf
- Aldrich, J. (2004). The discovery of comparative advantage. *Journal of the History of Economic Thought*, 26(3), 379-399. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1042771042000263858>
- Ali, S. B., Arif, K., Galani, S. Q., Ali, H., & Rehman, N. A. (2022). Do all financial economists speak the language of positivism? *International Journal of Social Science & Entrepreneurship*, 2(2), 532–545. <https://doi.org/10.58661/ijssse.v2i2.119>
- Ali, S. B., Arif, K., Galani, S. Q., Khan, Z. S., & Mubeen, M. (2022). A review on valuation and corporate finance. *Periodicals of Social Sciences*, 2(2). <https://psocialsciences.com/poss/index.php/poss/article/view/37>
- Arif, K., Isa, C. R., & Mustapha, M. Z. (2023). A Review of the Corporate Governance Structure of Pakistan. *JISR management and social sciences & economics*, 21(2), 41–58. <https://doi.org/10.31384/jisrmsse/2023.21.2.3>
- Arif, K., Isa, C. R., & Mustapha, M. Z. (2023). Do powerful CEOs benefit firm performance in Pakistan? *Asian Journal of Business and Accounting*, 75–106. <https://doi.org/10.22452/ajba.vol16no2.3>
- Awdel, Z. M. Odel, N. M. & Saadi, W. F. (2020). The Rise of Globalization and Its Effect on the Autonomy of State and Political Economy: *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7 (6), 998-1000. Retrieved from <http://dx.doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.06.171>.
- Bumbure, I. (2014). *Effects of Globalization on Developing Countries: A Case Study of the Baltic States*: Bahcesehir University Institute of Social Sciences. 1-55. <https://hdl.handle.net/20.500.14719/83>
- Dahlman, C. (2007). Technology, globalization, and international competitiveness: Challenges for developing countries. *Industrial development for the 21st century: Sustainable development perspectives*, 29-83.
- Dash S, Rath S, & Pati U. (2018). Financial Globalization and its Impact on Human Development: A Comparative Analysis of India, Singapore, and Japan. *Revista Espacios*, 39(14), 20-38. <https://www.revistaespacios.com/a18v39n14/18391420.html>
- Dowrick, S., & Golley, J. (2004). Trade openness and growth: who benefits? *Oxford review of economic policies*, 20(1), 38-56. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxrep/grh003>
- Haseeb, M., Suryanto, T., Hartani, N. H., & Jermisittiparsert, K. (2020). Nexus between globalization, income inequality and human development in Indonesian economy: evidence from application of partial and multiple wavelet coherence. *Social Indicators Research*, 147(3), 723-745. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication>.

- Karras, G. (2003). Trade openness and economic growth can we estimate the precise effect? <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1225622>
- Lee, E., & Vivarelli, M. (2006). The social impact of globalization in the developing countries. *Int'l Lab. Rev.*, 145, 167. <https://hdl.handle.net/10419/33211>
- Markusen, J. R., & Venables, A. J. (1998). Multinational firms and the new trade theory. *Journal of international economics*, 46(2), 183-203. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996\(97\)00052-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-1996(97)00052-4)
- Mun, T. (1621). *A discourse of trade, from England unto the East-Indies: Answering to diverse objections which are usually made against the same*. In *Early English Books Online*. University of Michigan Library Digital Collections. <https://name.umdl.umich.edu/A07886.0001.001>
- Olagunju K, Ogunniyi A. Oguntegbe K. F, & Oluwole. I. (2019). *Welfare Impact of Globalization in Developing Countries: Examining the Mediating Role of Human Capital*. *Economies*. 7: 84-108. <https://doi.org/10.3390/economies7030084>
- Raghutla, C. (2020). The effect of trade openness on economic growth: Some empirical evidence from emerging market economies: *Journal of Public Affairs*. 20 (3), 1-8. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pa.2081>.
- Raghutla, C., Sakthivel, P., Sampath, T., & Chittedi, K. R. (2018). Macroeconomic variables and stock prices in emerging economies: A panel analysis. *Theoretical and Applied Economics*, 25(3), 91–1.
- Sabi, M. (2007). *Globalization and Human Development*. International Conference on Globalization and Its Discontents, Cortland. 102-119. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/6989903.pdf>
- Smith, A. (1776). *The Wealth of Nations*. *Oxford University Press*.
- Tang, S., Wang, Z., Yang, G., & Tang, W. (2020). What Are the Implications of Globalization on Sustainability? A Comprehensive Study. *Sustainability*, 12(8), 3411. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12083411>
- Zeren, F., & Ari, A. (2013). Trade openness and economic growth: A panel causality test. *International journal of business and social science*, 4(9). http://ijbssnet.com/journals/Vol_4_No_9_August_2013/32.pdf